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TECHNOLOGY ADDICTION IN THE ATTENTION ECONOMY AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

Asst. Prof. Dr. Adnan Veysel ERTEMEL Istanbul Commerce University

Abstract: 21st century digitized environment is characterized with attention economy (Davenport, 2001). Digital platforms strive to grab users' attention. In return, they provide entertaining and informative content. This economy monetizes users' attention by selling advertisements. Lately, digital platforms employ behavioral psychology to increase online time by using sophisticated techniques to hook users thereby boosting their revenues (Eyal, 2014; Ertemel, 2016; Ertemel, Aydın, 2018). Therefore, this study argues that technology addiction is an architected phenomenon naturally resulting from attention economy. This paper suggests that looking at the phenomenon from sole psychological perspective is not enough to remedy this problem. In contrast, it's argued that deep understanding of the techniques and design constructs is obligatory to tackle this problem. The study proposes steps that could be taken to unhook users from those addictive experiences.

Keywords: Technology Addiction, Smartphone Addiction, Attention Economy

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